

„Museumspath“ Zollverein – Ways through the industrial heritage

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Introduction:

In 1847 the story of Zollverein began with the sinking of the first shaft in Essen Katernberg. Only four years later the first coal was conveyed from a depth of 110 meters. The claim with a size of 13 km² was further developed and at this time there were four collieries with eleven shafts. Due to efficiency and modernisation measures the central colliery with shaft XII was opened. At this time Zollverein was one of the largest and most modern mines of the world.

After a production time of 54 years shaft XII was closed and the production period on the claim ended after 135 years. With the closure the colliery became a monument. In 2001 the cultural landscape and the colliery Zollverein were listed as a world heritage by the UNESCO. Listed are the colliery shaft XII, colliery shaft 1/2/8 and the coking plant.

Insight

In accordance with the statutes of the Foundation Zollverein the purpose is making the monument and world heritage Zollverein shaft XII an accessible experience. With the development and realization of guided tours along a circuit through the former decking plant we fulfill this duty. This so called „museumspath“ was created by the „Bauhütte Zeche Zollverein Schacht XII“ in 1998 and since 1999 the Foundation Zollverein is carrying on with it. Before arranging the museumspath there were only occasional guided tours by former miners and alumni. With increasing demand regular guided tours were initiated.

By now the Foundation Zollverein managed to increase the number of visitors from 20.000 (1998) up to 72.000 (2006) per year.

The „museumspath“ includes the plant and machinery in its original state which explains the way of the coal aboveground. This way makes the industrial heritage Zollverein accessible. It is a distinctive feature that the admission is restricted to guided tours.

Outlook

By suggestion of the office for preservation of monuments and historical buildings in 2005 the Foundation Zollverein got the order from its curatorship to work out a concept of the presentation „the way of the coal“ during guided tours. The previous stations of the tour will be updated and with new stations in the coal washing plant both parts will be reassimilated. Preparing the location Zollverein and the museumspath for future requirements is part of the plan to make it an attractive experience for all visitors. The concept attaches great importance to a visitor appealing presentation in line with generally accepted conservation practice.

With the closure in 1986 all machines were shutdown and cannot be put into operation again. Even if selected machines were put into operation again for presentation it would only be possible to show their basic functions. Therefore it is a duty of the museumspath to show and explain the partial complicated function in a lucent and comprehensible way without derogating the listed matter.

Perspective

The museumspath enables us to show the industrial heritage of the colliery Zollverein to our visitors and provide future generations an insight into the world of this colliery.